

THE CHALLENGES OF BUSINESSES IN IMPLEMENTING A WORK FROM HOME POLICY IN SERVICE INDUSTRY: A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY

Varnima Sharma

Research Scholar, School of Commerce and Management, Career Point University, Kota

Sandeep Kumar

Research Supervisor Cum Associate Professor, School of Commerce and Management, Career Point University, Kota

ABSTRACT

There are many industries in which employees are doing work from home and in which one is service industry. In Service Industry employees are doing work from home are facing many challenges in implanting this policy. Challenges like communication, Job satisfaction, Work life balance, HR practices etc. Work from home has affected the lives of many people so here we will find out how employees are overcoming these challenges while doing work from home. There are still many businesses in Service Industry in which employees are doing work from home. Now with the pace of increasing this policy of work from home some employees are finding benefits and some are not. It has benefits as flexibility, improving retention of employees, if performing better work then increasing productivity also. It has negative aspects, as staff may feel isolated in doing work from home, development, lack of information also. The relationship between both employer and employee has become a circle of giving and taking benefits in which everyone is involved.

Keywords: Remote work, Employee Productivity, Efficiency, Human Resource Management, Job Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

The focus will be on Service Industry in which there are many businesses where employees are doing work from home. Our country is developing and is growing with many facilities as infrastructure and connectivity. Employees are facing many challenges in adopting the work from home policy we need to find out how they are adopted the challenges are what problems employees faced in implementing these changes. Here need to find ou problems and challenges in adopting the policy. There might be problem of collaborating and communicating with the employer with their location also plus working hours is also a challenge. There is need to identifying the challenges for work from home policy in Service industry so that there is development of different strategies to keep employees motivated and productive.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Authors	Journal/Articles	Conclusions
Amin Al- Habaibeh, Mathew Watkins, Kafel Waried and Maryam Bathaei Javareshk 2021	<i>Challenges and opportunities of remotely working from home during Covid-19 pandemic</i> Science Direct Research Review, (3), 99-108	The study was conducted during the pandemic for the employees who are doing work from home. The situation of the pandemic has forced the employees to use work from home practices. Many employees were facing difficulty in the beginning, as they do not know how

		to use the tools. It was concluded that work from home has advantages, as there is no travelling cost it saves time and has negative impact as well. In the pandemic employees learned how to adopt new technology.
Balazs Aczel, Marton Kovacs, Tanja van der Lippe and Barnabas Szaszi 2020	<i>Researchers working from home: Benefits and challenges</i> PLOS ONE Research Review, 16(3)	The study tells us that there is a flexibility in employees while doing work from home. It is playing important role in increasing efficiency and creating a good work life balance. Sample was collected of 704 academics who are doing work from home and it was found that there is decreased in the efficiency in employees who are doing work from home. It concludes that by following different strategies employees can do work from home in effective way and can maintain a healthy lifestyle.
Abriham Engidaw 2022	<i>Small businesses and their challenges during COVID-19 pandemic in developing countries: in case of Ethiopia</i> Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship Research Review, 11(1), 1-14	The study focuses on challenges of small businesses during the pandemic in different countries. It was found that there were large number of small businesses who got affected in the pandemic and this was very challenging as how to overcome the situation all should work in new markets.
Mohamed Mousa and Hala A Abdelgaffar 2021	<i>Work from Home in the Public Sector Context Post Covid-19: Challenges and Barriers</i> Global Encyclopedia of Public Administration, Public Policy and Governance Research Review, 1-6	The study focuses on how people will learn doing work from home in order to be safe from pandemic and protect the environment. It was found that there were many challenges that were faced by the public. It concludes that various precautionary steps must be taken in order to prevent challenges and allow public sector employees too to do work from home in order to maintain good process with the employees.
Frabcais 2021	<i>Teleworking in the Covid-19 pandemic: Trends and prospects</i> OCED Policy Response to Coronavirus Research Review, 1-19	The study tells that the pandemic has created a need for all the employees to do work from home and has created impact on the employees to low incomes. There were very large number of businesses who continue to do work from home and stated taking care of tools as videoconferencing, online meetings. It was concluded that employer and

		employees need to opt work from home and maintain good network and use of technology and internet access.
Salima Hamouche 2021	<i>Human resource management and the COVID-19 crisis: implications, challenges, opportunities, and future organizational directions</i> Journal of Management and Organization Research Review, 1-16	The study tells that there is challenging environment for both managers and human resource management; they need to find out measures to help their employees so that they can cope up with the situation. It was concluded that organizations must maintain measures for the employees but not possible to overcome long term challenges. So effective ways should be there in order to do work from home effectively then can cope up with long term challenges also and opportunities for the employees.
Mrs. Helen Sha Diana and Ms Janan 2021	<i>A Study on Challenges faced by CSR Company Employees Work From Home During Lockdown</i> International Advanced Research of Journal in Science, Engineering and Technology Research Review, 8(8), 304-308	The study tells that CSR is very important for many companies. The pandemic has given many offers to the businesses to use their resources properly towards more authentic CSR and need to address environmental challenges. CSR has provided many opportunities to both economic and social interest. The study concludes that CSR has now playing very important role in many businesses globally as this is crucial challenge for many businesses.
Abdullah Faiz Hassan and Vizayer Raj 2021	<i>Working from home during COVID-19 challenges solution for Maldives employees</i> International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Science Research Review, 9(11), 1622-1633	The study focuses on the pandemic that many countries are been forced to adopt challenges as to maintain social distancing to follow various protocols. Though this pandemic has given many chances to the business and employees and also provides flexibility, increases motivation. It concludes that there should be increase in productivity and performance of the employees and should time on their health. According to the study work from home has not been proved good for the employees in Maldives.
Naoyuki Yoshino and Farhad Taghizadeh Hesary 2016	<i>Major challenges facing small and medium sized enterprises in Asia and solutions for Mitigating them</i> Asian Development Bank Institute	The study focuses on small and medium sized enterprises for Asian country and economy. SME's plays a very important role in economy. It has many challenges as finance, expenses. It concludes that there is

	Research Review,1-19	an increase in completion to adapt the faster changing environment various market demand, technological changes should be adopted, resources should be used in effective way, need to contribute more information in many aspects.
Ahmad al-rfou 2021	<i>Remote working environment challenges in the context of the covid-19 pandemic</i> Journal of Asian Business Strategy Research Review, (11), 95-103	The study focuses on employees who have started doing work from home in the pandemic and this has resulted in many environmental challenges. There were 125 responses collected from different employees. It concludes that there should be increase in level of practices in employees doing work from home. As if they not work properly them there is decrease in level of their performance of their jobs. IT industry too provides employees to do work remotely.
Arunima and Richa Nangia 2022	<i>Work from home and Covid-19: Encountering ethical issues in new normal</i> Asian Journal of Management Research Review, 1(13)	The study tells that pandemic has created both health crisis and nationwide economic threat. It has push down many businesses in lockdown across world. Many employees and employer were affected through this pandemic. Many people are struggling for effective management. It concludes that there should be proper delegation of authorities be follow better working conditions should be given to all the employees and motivation should be given so that their performance can be increased.
Chinnaiah PM Chythra P 2021	<i>Challenges of working from home in persistent covid-19 environment</i> International Research Journal of Business studies Research Review, (14), 85-97	The study tells that IT industry has contributed many things towards growth of the Indian economy. This industry has adopted many measures for the employees to do work from home and develop work from methods effectively for the employees. Earlier there were many challenges now it has changed into moderate challenges. Employees are being provided better working conditions and are motivated towards work and to work in effective and efficient manner.
Chokri Kooli 2022	<i>Challenges of working from home during the COVID-19 pandemic for women in UAE</i>	The study focuses on women who are doing work from home in United Arab Emirates during pandemic

	Journal of Public Affairs Research Review, 1(23)	lockdown. It was found that for women it is very challenging to do work from home in the pandemic because they need to manage household activities this was really affecting the loves of women. It was concluded that there may be a way to maintain their work life balance of women by drafting out legislations. There should be different policies programmed to ensure that women can do work efficiently in work from home and can manage their work life balance also.
Arlington 2020	<i>How organizations must manage a more complex hybrid workforce</i> Gartner Survey Research Review, July 14, 20	The study was done on Gartner survey which tells us that many company leader, HR, finance department are doing work from home. For many employees it was very new to adopt new system but many of them learned to manage their things and flex hour is one factor of this. Organizations who called their employees at the workplace are maintaining safety measures in order to protect them. It was concluded that Gartner HR practice plays a very important role in creating relevant human resource approaches so that employees can be offered to individual decision making and think on strategically how to perform the work.
Rebecca Stropoli 2021	<i>Are we really productive working from home</i> CBR Economics Research Review, August 18, 21	The study tells that employees who are doing work from home are they rally bringing productivity in their organizations. It concludes that work from home plays a significant role in this. Many employees learned to do work.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To Identify Key Challenges: *Objective:* Conduct a thorough literature review and empirical analysis to identify and categorize the key challenges faced by businesses in the service industry when implementing a work from home policy.

- To Analyze Employee Adaptability:** *Objective:* Assess the adaptability of employees in the service sector to remote work environments by conducting surveys, interviews, and case studies to understand their perspectives, concerns, and experiences.
- To Evaluate Technological Infrastructure:** *Objective:* Evaluate the existing technological infrastructure of service industry businesses to determine its suitability

for supporting remote work, focusing on network security, software compatibility, and communication tools.

3. **To Examine Managerial Strategies:** *Objective:* Investigate the strategies employed by managers in the service industry to facilitate effective communication, task management, and performance evaluation for remote employees, considering leadership styles and managerial techniques.
4. **To Assess Employee Productivity and Job Satisfaction:** *Objective:* Measure the impact of remote work on employee productivity and job satisfaction using quantitative and qualitative methods, comparing performance metrics and job satisfaction surveys between in-office and remote working scenarios.
5. **To Explore Legal and Compliance Issues:** *Objective:* Examine legal and compliance challenges faced by businesses in adhering to labor laws, data protection regulations, and employee rights in the context of remote work, analyzing relevant policies and legal cases.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Objective:

Literature Review and Meta-Analysis: The objective of this research is to systematically review and analyze existing literature on the Challenges of Businesses in Implementing a Work from Home Policy in Service Industry

DATA SOURCES:

Identification of Sources: Identify relevant academic journals, articles, conference papers, reports, and books related to remote work and its effects on employees. Utilize academic databases such as PubMed, Google Scholar, Scopus, and relevant organizational websites.

INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

Define specific criteria for including or excluding sources, such as publication date range, relevance, and academic rigor.

DATA COLLECTION:

Literature Search: Conduct systematic searches using appropriate keywords and search strings to identify relevant literature.

Data Extraction: Extract pertinent information from selected sources, including study objectives, methods, findings, and key variables related to productivity, well-being, and job satisfaction.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. The purpose of knowing the perception of the employees their likes and dislikes, and preferences in IT industry in work from home.
2. To know the importance of Technology is also playing a major role in today's scenario as it is essential for each and every individual.
3. To know whether employees are working in a flexible environment in doing work from home because if there is a flexibility then productivity will increase

CONCLUSION

1. Work from home is not only benefit but brings huge increase in organizational productivity.
2. Employees are grateful for the opportunity as there is proper surrounding and they are able to manage the working hours.
3. Employee's perspective provides valuable insights into multifaced dynamics of modern work arrangements.
4. The research adds to better knowledge of the pros and cons of remote work models by examining the experiences, opinions etc.
5. There is lack of physical activities this is the major challenge.
6. Work from home has reduced travel time and cost which has made employees more productive.

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